

THERMODYNAMIC STUDIES OF TREATMENT OF WASTEWATER FROM FOOD INDUSTRY, USING POWDERED SNAIL SHELL (PSS)

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Abstract

The thermodynamic studies of the treatment of wastewater from a food industry using powdered snail shell was done at different temperatures. The change in standard Gibb's free energy (ΔG^0) of pH has values of -0.109, -0.263, -0.147, 0, and -0.064 kJ/mol respectively, while the change in standard entropy (ΔS^0) and enthalpy (ΔH^0) have values of 0.80 and -279.9 kJ/mol respectively. ΔG^0 values of alkalinity were -0.359, -0.355, -0.354, -0.344 and -0.347 kJ/mol respectively, its values of ΔS^0 and ΔH^0 were -0.27 and -26.4 kJ/mol respectively. Turbidity has ΔG^0 values of -0.405, -0.338, -0.322, -0.161 and -0.145 kJ/mol while its ΔS^0 and ΔH^0 values were 1.68 and -599.6 kJ/mol. The values of ΔG^0 of electrical conductivity were -0.415, -0.587, -0.671, -0.263 and -0.240 kJ/mol while its ΔS^0 and ΔH^0 values were 1.50 and -591.5 kJ/mol respectively. ΔG^0 , ΔS^0 and ΔH^0 values of TS, TSS, TDS, BOD₅, COD, DO, NO₃-N, Phosphate, sulphate and Lead were also determined. However Cadmium could not be computed because it was below the detectable limit. The thermodynamic studies were done at 283K, 292K, 303K, 313K and 333K respectively. Physicochemical characterization of the wastewater was determined before and after treatment. However the food and mineral composition of four different species of snail shell were determined, the pH, surface area and optimum dosage of the powdered snail shell were determined, from the analysis, the giant African snail shell was chosen and used for the treatment of the wastewater, due to its large surface area, stability at pH of 4-12 and the ease to produce a fine powder when homogenised.

KEYWORDS: Thermodynamic studies, food industry, powdered snail shell, Temperature Wastewater.

Introduction: Many methods are available for the treatment of wastewater to produce an environmentally safe- fluid waste stream, or treated effluent and solid waste or treated sludge that can be reused or safe for disposal.

In general, there are various technological methods existing for the treatment of wastewater, such as chemical precipitation, ion exchange, adsorption, membrane processes, supercritical fluid extraction, bioremediation and oxidation with oxidizing agent (Asia and Oladoja, 2007).

However, most of these technologies are either extremely expensive or not too environmentally friendly in the treatment of water and wastewater.

Biosorption, a process whereby certain types of inactive dead biomass (such as snail shell, peat, rice husk, fruit peels) may bind and concentrate heavy metals from aqueous solution is considered as an alternative technology for the removal of heavy metals and other pollutants from wastewater and industrial effluent (Volesky, 2003; Naja and Mustin, 2005),

Efficient and environment friendly methods are thus needed to be developed. Biosorption technology is advantageous due to the cost effectiveness of biosorbent (biomass) because they are derived from cheap sources

Materials and Methods

Wastewater sample collection

The wastewater sample used for this study was collected by grab sampling technique from the discharge unit of a food processing company in Edo state Nigeria.

Analysis of samples were done in triplicate to ensure representative and reproducible results. The polymer container for the collection of wastewater was washed using distilled water; it was allowed to dry and some quantity of Manganese sulphate salt was added in the container, this was to fix the dissolved oxygen, since its determination was not carried out on site during collection

Analysis of wastewater

pH and temperature were determined on site and the wastewater was preserved at a temperature of 4°C for further analysis.

Analysis of the sample was done immediately as describe in APHA (1998) and Ademoroti (1996).

Thermodynamic Treatment

The thermodynamics such as change in standard free energy (ΔG^0), enthalpy (ΔH^0) and entropy (ΔS^0) were determined using the following equations:

$$\ln k_c = \frac{\Delta S^0}{R} - \frac{\Delta H^0}{RT} \text{-----} (1)$$

$$\Delta G_{ads} = \Delta H_{ads} - T \Delta S_{ads} \text{-----}(2)$$

Where R (8.314J/mol) is the gas constant, T is the absolute temperature and K_c (l/g) is the standard thermodynamic equilibrium constants defined by q_e/c_e , was obtained by a plot of $\ln K_c$ versus $1/T$ the values of ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 were estimated from the slope and the intercept.

Calculated amount (10 g) of powdered snail shell was weighed and poured into a 250 ml beaker containing 100 ml of wastewater, the beaker was placed inside another 500 ml beaker containing ice mixture to maintain the temperature at 283K, the mixture was stirred at regular intervals for 1hour, it was filtered and the filtrate analysed. The method was repeated for 293K, 303K, 313K, and 333K. The temperature was raised by the application of heat.

Results and Discussion

Physicochemical Parameters of Untreated and Treated Wastewater from Food Industry at Different Temperatures:

The treatment of wastewater at different temperatures is presented in Table2:

Table 1: Physicochemical parameters of treated wastewater from food industry at Different temperature

S/NO	Parameters	Units	FMES	Untreated wastewater	TEMPERATURE, K				
					283	293	303	313	333
1	pH		6.5-8.5	8.8±0.3	8.4	7.9	8.3	8.8	8.6
2	ALKALINITY	mg/L		27.6±0.5	582±0.4	586±0.6	589±0.5	594±0.8	598±0.7
3	TURBIDITY	mg/L	50	678±2.0	8.57±2.5	8.68±2.3	8.96±2.4	9.57±2.2	9.66±2.3
4	TDS	mg/L	250	10.18±0.3	64±0.5	68±0.4	69±0.7	73±0.4	79±0.6
5	TSS	mg/L	50	77±1.0	0.5±0.01	0.5±0.01	0.5±0.01	0.2±0.01	0.3±0.01
6	TS	mg/L		115.7±1.5	64.001±1.4	68.001±1.3	69.001±1.4	73.001±1.2	79.001±1.3
7	EC	µS/cm	100	194±0.1	128±0.2	120±0.3	117±0.4	138±0.4	140±0.2
8	BOD ₅	mg/L	40	152.7±0.6	98.45±0.5	101.43±0.4	101.43±0.2	126.32±0.4	210.43±0.1
9	COD	mg/L		959.3±1.2	248.83±0.3	265.83±0.2	324.62±0.4	420.84±0.3	514.58±0.2
10	DO	mg/L	>4.0	1806.18±0.5	5.03±0.4	4.21±0.5	4.14±0.6	3.56±0.4	3.45±0.5
11	PHOSPHATE	mg/L	5	3.10±0.1	1.21±0.01	1.21±0.01	1.21±0.01	1.21±0.01	1.24±0.01
12	SULPHATE	mg/L	240	1.53±0.1	2.81±0.02	2.84±0.02	2.81±0.2	2.83±0.02	2.84±0.02
13	NO ₃ -N	mg/L	40	3.326±0.1	1.04±0.01	1.03±0.01	1.06±0.01	1.06±0.01	1.01±0.01
14	Pb	mg/L	0.05	1.09±0.1	0.081±0.002	0.081±0.002	0.081±0.002	0.081±0.002	0.081±0.002
15	Cd	mg/L	0.05	1.013±0.3	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL

BDL: Below detectable limit

From Table 1, it was observed that the pH values increases with increase in temperature, but the values were within the range of 5-9 as recommended by FMES (1991). These values were the same as the findings reported by Fayemiwo and Adebisi, (2011) on physicochemical properties studies of industrial effluents in Ibadan. The increase in pH values were attributed to the degree of ionisation of substances as the temperature increases. There is the tendency that waste and other suspended solids and dissolved substances in the wastewater forms both positive and negative ions. Most of these positive ions can combine with the hydroxyl ion from the ionization of water to form alkaline substances that could increase the pH value of the wastewater during treatment at high temperature.

The same trend of increase in parameters with increase in temperature was also observed in alkalinity (582mg/l at 283K) and gradually increases with increase in temperature (598mg/l at 333K). Although these values in treated wastewater were lower than the values of alkalinity in untreated wastewater.

This increase in the values are traceable to the ionisation of substances at high temperature, hence there is increase in entropy at high temperature which leads to high degree of randomness of the system leading to reduction in the degree of adsorption of substances by the adsorbent.

Turbidity values in treated wastewater were lower than the values observed for untreated wastewater (8.57NTU) and there was increase in values as the temperature of treatment wastewater increases. Although, the values were still lower than that of the untreated wastewater. This is an indication that the treated wastewater contains low dissolved substances and suspended solid.

There was 98 percent reduction of total suspended solid (0.3mg/l). This shows that filterable or suspended solids were removed by powdered snail shell at any temperature. However, there was still some amount of dissolved solids in the wastewater which increases with increase in temperature.

The essence of this increase is that at a high temperature there is high degree of dissolution of substance, to the extent that at 333K, the values of the dissolved solids were almost the same as that of the untreated wastewater. This is because at that temperature there is the tendency of some of the powdered snail shell to enter into solution, hence it is advisable to carry out treatment of wastewater using powdered snail shell at low temperature so as to achieve optimum treatment.

There were fluctuations in the values of electrical conductivity, but the values were higher at high temperature. This is as a result of the fact that at high temperature, there are high degrees of ionisation and mobility of ions.

The COD and BOD values were 248.83mg/l and 98.45mg/l at 283K. There was increase in values with increase in the temperature of treated wastewater. However these values were lower than those of the untreated wastewater. This shows that there is reduction in the degree of adsorption at high temperature.

There was decrease in dissolved oxygen at higher temperature; this is obvious because there is increase in the utilization of dissolved oxygen by substances for oxidation, since oxidation increases with increase in temperature. The rate at which dissolve oxygen escapes from the wastewater was high as the temperature of the system increases.

There was no significant increase in the values of phosphate, sulphate and $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ even at high temperature, although the values were higher at high temperature for phosphate. There was adsorption of these substances at the temperature for which the wastewater was treated.

The values of lead were the same at all the temperature for wastewater treatment. However cadmium was below detection limits at any temperature. This indicates their absence in the wastewater from food industry.

Thermodynamic Studies of Treated Wastewater from Food Industry:

The wastewater from food industry was treated at different temperatures to obtain optimum temperature for treatment. The data obtained were subjected to thermodynamic model using the Van't Hoff equation; $\Delta G = -RT \ln K_{ad}$ where ΔG^0 is the Gibb's free energy, R is the gas constant (8.314J/mol), T is the Temperature, K is the adsorption constant. A plot of ΔG^0 against T was made (Mckay and Ho., 1999) as presented in Figures 1 - 5 below:

Fig1 : Plot of ΔG against T of treated wastewater from food industry

Fig2: Plot of ΔG against T of treated wastewater from food industry

Fig 3 : Plot of ΔG against T of treated wastewater from food industry

Fig 4: plot of ΔG against T of treated wastewater from food industry

Fig 5 : Plot of ΔG against T of treated wastewater from food industry

The values of ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 were determined from the slope and the intercept respectively. The thermodynamic data were presented in the Table 2

Table2: THERMODYNAMIC DATA OF TREATMENT OF WASTEWATER FROM FOOD INDUSTRY

PARAMETERS	ΔG^0 (kJ/mol)					ΔS^0 (kJ/mol)	ΔH^0 (kJ/mol)	
	TEMPERATURE(K)	283	293	303	313			333
pH		-0.109	-0.263	-0.147	0	-0.064	0.80	-279.9
Alkalinty		-0.359	-0.355	-0.354	-0.344	-0.347	-0.27	-26.4
Turbidity		-0.405	-0.338	-0.322	-0.161	-0.145	1.68	-599.6
EC		-0.415	-0.587	-0.671	-0.263	-0.240	1.50	-591.5
TS		-2.609	-2.553	-2.604	-2.543	-2.487	-1.84	-219.2
TSS		-27.43	-28.40	-29.37	-30.56	-32.28	-59.59	9137.6
TDS		-0.435	-0.303	-0.276	-0.139	-0.078	30.05	-982.9
BOD		-5.356	-5.473	-5.660	-5.276	-4.200	2.46	-23.35
COD		-	-	-	-	-2.205	-12.177	-4904.1
DO		4.664	4.508	4.323	3.791			
NO ₃ -N		1.201	1.011	0.891	0.792	0.788	-16.28	780.6
Phosphate		-	-	-	-	-0.211	-0.605	148.0
		0.110	0.138	0.070	0.073			
Sulphate		-	-	-	-	-0.649	-1.23	193.86
		0.552	0.572	0.591	0.610			
Pb		-	-	-	-	-0.437	-0.664	76.39
		0.396	0.411	0.407	0.420			
Cd		-5.943	-6.154	-6.363	-6.574	-6.994	-13.25	2087.9
		NC	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC

NC: Not computed

From Table3, it can be observed that the value of ΔG^0 is negative with the exception of dissolved oxygen which has a positive ΔG^0 . The negative value of ΔG^0 is an indication that the treatment of the wastewater at different temperature is a spontaneous process.

The positive value of ΔG^0 for dissolved oxygen shows the change in dissolved oxygen is not spontaneous, hence it required external factor for the increase in dissolved oxygen during treatment at different temperatures to be possible. This can be explained on the premise that at increase in temperature, the dissolved oxygen decreases, because oxygen will be liberated from the wastewater.

This is evident from the positive value of ΔH^0 , which indicates that there was increase in dissolved oxygen at lower temperatures hence the endothermic nature of treatment of dissolved oxygen.

The negative values of ΔS^0 of most of the parameters correspond to decrease in the degrees of freedom of the adsorbed species which also indicate that the adsorption process in the treatment of wastewater from food industry is stable, as there is increase in orderliness of the system (Babalola *et al.*, 2009).

The decrease in the adsoption of waste which is reflected from the increase in most of the parameters at increase in temperature may have resulted from the weakening in the adsorptive forces between the active site of the adsorbent and adsorbate species and also between the adjacent molecule of the adsorbed phase (Pandy *et al.*,1986).

ΔH^0 values for some parameters were positive, such parameters as TSS, DO, $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$, Phosphate, sulphate and Pb, this indicates that their reduction at different temperatures is endothermic, this can be seen from the increase in the values of the parameters at increase in temperature. Babalola *et al.*, (2009) reported a similar result in the thermodynamic studies of the biosorption of cadmium(ii) and lead(ii) from aqueous solution by *Tralium tranguare* (water leaf).

Conclusion

The thermodynamic studies of the treatment of the wastewater revealed that the change in free energy (ΔG^0) for most of the physicochemical parameters has negative values. This confirms the feasibility of the treatment process and the spontaneous nature of the adsorption of the dissolved solid substance by the powdered snail shell during treatment.

The increase in values of most parameters at high temperatures is an indication that optimum treatment was achieved at low temperature.

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